

LATIN AND GREC TERMINOLOGY IN THE PROCESS OF STUDY OF OPERATIVE SURGERY

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Annotation. The article discusses the problem of the prevalence of foreign terms in the field of operative surgery. We reveal the definition of ways to replenish the vocabulary of the “medical” language. Expressions borrowed from other languages, such as Latin and Greek, are described.

Key words: borrowing, medical terminology, operative surgery, medicine, international vocabulary.

Medicine is a science known to mankind since ancient times, therefore a natural process in the development of medical knowledge is the improvement and complication of its terminology, which has its own characteristics. Firstly, medical terminology has reached a high degree of internationalization compared to the terminologies of other branches of knowledge. This is explained by the fact that medicine began to develop from ancient Greece, therefore one of the main languages of medicine is Greek. Many terms are found, first of all, in the “Hippocratic Collection” (“Corpus Hippocratum”). It can be said that the history of European medicine and medical terminology began with him. The second most important language in medical terminology is the Latin language, despite the fact that it “died” in the 8th-9th centuries; all scientific medical works were created only in Latin [3].

In the 12th century there was a revolution in the formation of new scientific disciplines and fundamental scientific directions, which, of course, entailed the formation of new terms. Naturally, this also affected medicine.

Medical terminology is the language that helps doctors from different specialties and countries understand each other. It must be clear to medical professionals, because they need to use medical terminology in their professional field. The most important requirement for a term in medicine is to reflect the essence of a phenomenon or subject;

it must be accepted by the majority of specialists. The semantic meaning of a particular term in medicine only becomes public knowledge when it is fixed by a precise term that does not allow different interpretations, be simple and unambiguous [8].

Operative surgery, like all medicine, has been studied by man since ancient times. It is not surprising that in its terminological system, in addition to the native words of its national language, one can also find terms that were taken from other languages [1]. In the medical vocabulary of operative surgery there are terms from various languages: Greek, Latin, Arabic, English, French and other European languages. It is well known that operative surgery is an integrative science, which means that surgical medical vocabulary can be used by specialists of many specialties, for example, anesthesiologists, surgeons, otolaryngologists, obstetricians and gynecologists. Terminology in the field of operative surgery has undergone many changes and additions in the process of its development, so surgical vocabulary can be separated into a separate area of the terminosphere. In the vocabulary of operative surgery, to this day there is an integration of various foreign terms, mainly Latin and Greek, and this is a feature of this area in medicine [2].

In our time, due to the creation of new methods and methods of surgical interventions, the problem of language borrowing has resumed. Because of this, a "struggle" has emerged between traditional and new terms that relate to operative surgery. To solve such a complex issue, we need to generally understand what constitutes linguistic borrowing. Borrowing is one of the ways to enrich the vocabulary of a particular scientific field, which is the introduction of foreign terms into the terminology, which become an integral part of the vocabulary of a scientific discipline [4].

The study of the processes that have occurred and are occurring in the medical terminological system is important and relevant. Any term in the field of operative surgery is a kind of carrier and keeper of knowledge, and, therefore, carries certain information about the human body, which once again emphasizes the importance of understanding and correct interpretation of a particular term.

The relevance of studying various foreign terms also lies in the need for a modern surgeon, medical student and other specialists in the field of medicine to be savvy in matters of operative surgery and to understand numerous foreign and complex terms. Naturally, with the progress of progress in medical practice, in particular in surgery, the

latest developments and new equipment will be introduced, so it is obvious that it is necessary to expand scientific ties between doctors from different countries, and, therefore, the issue of medical terminology will be increasingly relevant.

The terms of any discipline and operative surgery in particular carry certain, accurately recorded information about any action or subject, therefore, their correct understanding is the key to success in every case [5].

Greek and Latin terminology includes all the important concepts and terms of medicine, without which medicine itself could not exist. The main criterion for a term is its meaning in modern medical terminology. Foreign concepts and words create certain difficulties that students may objectively encounter when studying this medical discipline. Foreign terminology increases scientific motivation and interest in the subject of operative surgery, broadens the horizons of students and creates the prerequisites for a more in-depth study of the subject. After all, in order to understand the semantic connotation of a term, it is necessary to understand its etymology and know its origin.

Medical terminology and operative surgery are based on words of Latin and Greek origin, and these words are quite complexly composed of a root (although there may be several roots), a prefix and a suffix.

The use of Greek terms dates back to the times of Hippocrates (c. 400-365 BC), Claudius Galen (131-201 AD) and their predecessors. Latin terms from Aulus Corvelius Celsus, a Roman encyclopedist of the 1st century AD. Later, terms were formed almost exclusively on the same Greco-Latin basis. In Russia, the borrowing of medical terms began only in the 19th century. from Europe.

A medical university student, resident, or surgeon can definitely encounter problems and difficulties when using professional vocabulary that consists of foreign language terms. For example, alloplasty, alloplastica (from the Greek allos another, plasso mold), asepsis, aseptica (from the Greek a denial, septikos putrefactive, causing decay), aerocystotomy, aērocystotomia (from the Greek aēr air, kystis bubble, tomia dissection, incision), vascularization, vascularisatio (from Latin vasculum small vessel). Naturally, foreign language vocabulary in medical terminology is difficult to understand, assimilate and apply this knowledge in practice, making it difficult for representatives of individual medical disciplines to communicate.

At the same time, Greco-Latin terms, occupying a significant place in operative surgery, are fully mastered and serve as the basis for the creation of new words already on Russian soil. They are easy to use, mostly unambiguous and used in regular word-formation patterns, and are currently the main ones. And, knowing many foreign morphemes, one can predict the meaning of a particular term that is used in the study of operative surgery.

Words of Latin origin with the endings "tio", "sio", "xio" are formed from verbs and mean an action, process or result of an action. For example, amputation means cutting off, taking away a part of the body (from amputare - to cut off), aspiratio - penetration of foreign substances, foreign bodies into the respiratory tract), literally - inhalation, aspiration (verb mpirare - to inhale).

The suffix "oma" indicates a tumor: adenoma - a true glandular tumor (aden - gland), angioma - a tumor from blood vessels (angi - vessel), atheroma - a sebaceous gland cyst due to blockage of the excretory duct (other - ear, arrow), fibroadenoma - benign tumor of glandular and connective tissue (fibr – fiber, aden – gland) [7].

Based on the above, it should be noted that words of foreign origin occupy a large share in the vocabulary of the sublanguage of operative surgery, reflecting the process of interconnection of different languages.

The terminology of modern surgery is one of the most complex terminological systems. The centuries-old history of the formation of surgical terminology proves that surgical vocabulary is constantly undergoing processes of change and improvement, and the introduction of ever new foreign terminology. Naturally, this causes fear and uncertainty for students who are just beginning to learn the basics of operative surgery. After all, such an abundance of surgical medical terms (according to experts, the terminological fund of modern medicine exceeds 500 thousand medical terms, more than 20 different languages) can confuse students in the process of studying operative surgery. Previously, when there were much fewer terms and concepts, a surgeon could perfectly navigate the terminology known to him. And now, with the advent of more and more new borrowed words, it is simply impossible to master hundreds of thousands of concepts (historical information: in the 10th century there were 1 thousand medical terms, in 1850 - about 6 thousand, in 1950 - about 45 thousand) [6].

It is necessary to know foreign vocabulary in operative surgery, which will allow you to understand foreign words in surgical terminology used in medical literature, in educational films, at seminars and conferences.

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